

Malnutrition Influencing Factors In Under-Five Children: A Descriptive Tertiary Care Hospital-Based Study, India

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 19, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: September 26, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Malnutrition, Under-Five Children, Undernutrition, Anthropometry, Mother</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5528853</p>	<p><i>Background and objectives: Malnutrition is one of the major concerns and public health problems worldwide in a few under-developing countries. The disparities in the prevalence of malnutrition across geographical areas and within populations are due to poverty and underprivileged social environment rather than biomedical causes. The study aimed to identify the factors affecting malnutrition among under-five children admitted to tertiary care hospitals, India.</i></p> <p><i>Method and study design: The study was a descriptive survey design. The researcher screened 850 under-five children's anthropometric status to rule out the malnutrition status of the child. 142 under-five children found malnutrition admitted to tertiary care hospital. The non-probability convenience sampling technique was used to collect the data from the participants.</i></p> <p><i>Results: The regression analysis showed that as factors influencing malnutrition increases malnutrition in under-five children increases. There is an apparent positive correlation between antenatal, weaning, and immunization status and illness factors and malnutrition ($p < 0.001$) indicating that for an increase of inadequate antenatal care (0.050), uncertain in providing exclusive breastfeeding up to 6month (0.146), inappropriate amount of nutritious food introduced during the weaning period and fail to continue breastfeeding up to 2years of age (0.024), fail to take immunization as per national immunization schedule and illness encountered during the under-five period (0.044) showed increase in malnutrition and also showed malnutrition negatively correlated with diet /lifestyle during pregnancy ($p < 0.001$). It implies malnutrition is (-0.018) less with diet and lifestyle adopted during pregnancy.</i></p> <p><i>Conclusion: Immediate identification and strengthening of public health intervention for mild malnutrition are important and effective implementation and evaluation planning is essential to prevent malnutrition among under-five children.</i></p>

Introduction

Nutrition has a major role in the growth and development of every individual. When the quality and quantity are deficient of food consumed by the individual he or she may suffer from malnutrition. Malnutrition is one of the major concerns worldwide and a public health problem in India. ¹The disparity in the prevalence of malnutrition across geographical areas and within populations is due to poverty and underprivileged social environment rather than biomedical causes. But in the past two decades, global trends have shown progress, with the prevalence rates of underweight falling from around 38% in the eighties to around 25% presently. ²The millennium development goal for child mortality aims to reduce by two thirds the under-five mortality rate between 2000 and 2015 and in the developing countries tackling malnutrition is the biggest challenge in achieving the goal. ³

The under-five malnutrition problem in India is a widespread phenomenon that is, a relatively small number of states, districts, and villages account for a large share of the malnutrition burden, only 5 states and 50% of villages account for about 80% of the malnutrition burden. ⁴Each year approximately 2.3 million deaths among 6-60 months aged children in developing countries are associated with malnutrition, which is about 41% of the total deaths in this age group. A recent study among children aged between 3months to 3years of age conducted in 130 districts through demographic and Health Surveys in 53 countries over a period from 2012-2017 found that variance in mild under-weight has a larger and more robust correlation with child mortality than the variance in severe under-weight. The study concluded that the prevalence of mild under-weight deserves greater attention as a useful signal of changing public health conditions among children in developing countries.

Therefore, the health system needs to detect malnutrition at an early stage for planning and implementing timely interventions (International Food Policy 2015).

The World Health Organization (WHO) estimated that malnutrition is associated with about half of the 10.7 million child deaths among under-five children occurring each year in the developing world.⁵⁻⁷ Nearly half of all deaths in children under five are attributable to under-nutrition. Undernutrition puts children at greater risk of dying from common infections, increases the frequency and severity of such infections, and contributes to delayed recovery.⁸⁻¹² The interaction between under-nutrition and infection can create a potentially lethal cycle of worsening illness and deteriorating nutritional status.¹³ Poor nutrition in the first 1,000 days of a child's life can also lead to stunted growth, which is associated with impaired cognitive ability and reduced school and work performance.

As per the latest global estimates, India has a higher proportion of stunted children than Africa (32%), a number that is almost three times more than Latin America. In India, the prevalence of stunting in children less than five years of age is 39%, according to the latest 2013-14 national survey of the Ministry of Women and Child Development. This represents a decline of 19.4% since the previous survey in 2005-06.⁸⁻¹⁰ The health system needs to detect malnutrition at an early stage for planning and implementing timely interventions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample and Design: This study was used a descriptive survey design and used convenience sampling to recruited and enrol 142 under-five malnutrition children admitted in tertiary care hospitals from 2018 to 2020. The validity of the tool was obtained from experts from various fields. Weighing scale, infantometer and stadiometer were used to assess the weight, length and height of the under-five children. The weighing scale was calibrated to ensure the accuracy of the instruments. Test and re-rest method was used to assess the reliability (>0.8) of the tool on factors influencing malnutrition. The weight and height survey was carried out among 850 under-five to identify malnutrition status. The final sample was recruited for the study was 142 under-five children who showed mild, moderate and severe malnutrition status as shown in (Fig-1) An interview session was held with the mothers of those 142 malnourished under-five children to detect the factors influencing malnutrition among their children.

Sampling frame

Measures

Demographic characteristics: Demographic characteristics of under-five children surveyed in children were age in the month, gender, types and illness delivery, and surgical history, birth order of the child, Number of siblings below 5 years and primary caretaker details. In mother's of under-five children consists of age, religion, age at marriage and childbirth, education and occupation and socioeconomic status, parity and types of family.

Anthropometric assessment: Weighing scale, infantometer and stadiometer were used to assess the weight, length and height of the under-five children. The weighing scale was calibrated to ensure the accuracy of the instruments. The weight and height survey was carried out among 850 under-five to diagnose malnutrition status. The final sample was recruited for the study was 142 under-five children who showed mild, moderate and severe malnutrition status. The weight and height parameters were assessed and the result was interpreted by Gomez classification.

Structured interview questionnaires: An interview session was held with the mothers of those 142 malnourished under-five children to detect the factors influencing malnutrition among their children. The study was explained and consent was obtained from the under-five mothers. The participants were ensured about the confidentiality of their responses. The interview session questionnaires consist of antenatal care with 6 items with sum scores ranges from (0-6), diet and lifestyle during pregnancy with 5 items with sum scores range from (0-4), feeding pattern during pregnancy with 3 items with sum score ranges from (0-3), breastfeeding and weaning pattern with 9 items with sum score ranges from (0-9) and immunization history and illness encountered during under-five age with 6 items with sum score ranges from (0-6). Test and re-rest method was used to assess the reliability (>0.8) of the factor influencing malnutrition tool.

Ethical consideration

Prior written permission was obtained from the Yenepoya (Deemed to be University) Ethics Committee (Protocol No: 2018/152) and the hospital authority. The study was explained and consent was obtained from the under-five mothers. The participants were ensured about the confidentiality of their responses.

Data Analysis

Data were computed in IBM SPSS software version 23.0 to analyze descriptive and inferential statistics. Malnutrition status of the under-five children identified by frequency and percentage. Factor influencing malnutrition was assessed by linear regression coefficient to identify the relationship between malnutrition with factors influencing malnutrition among under-five children. The present study is compared socio-demographic variables with malnutrition status of the under-five children by chi-square χ^2 test. The sample size was determined by using a single population proportion with 95% CI and marginal error of 5%, by taking a maximum value of 50% and population portion of 850 under-five children admitted in the tertiary care hospital. The final sample decided was 142 malnourished under-five children and mothers of the identified mild, moderate and severe malnutrition under-five children.

Results

The majority 24.6% belonged to 6month-11months, 52.1% were females, 54.9% of the mothers underwent normal delivery, 75.3%, 68.3% of the children were healthy and had no surgical history respectively. 30.2% belonged to third in birth order, 33.8% had more than three siblings, 92.9% children's primary caretaker was mother, and 62.6% were belonging to the Muslim religion. 31.6%, 37.3% education status of the father and mother was up to high school respectively. 35.9% of the father's occupation status was a private employee.

Malnutrition according to age and gender among under-five children

Mild, moderate, severe malnutrition in a male and female under-five child is shown in (table: 2) the majority (52.9%) of male children < 6 months of age had severe malnutrition and (45.5%) of girls had mild malnutrition. Age group of 6-11month majority (80%) boys had mild and moderate malnutrition and (66.6%) of the girls were moderately nourished. Between 12-23month the majority (75%) of boys had moderate malnutrition and (29.6%) of the girls were moderately nourished. The majority (57%) of the boys between the age group of 24-35months had severe malnutrition and (25%) girls were moderately nourished. Among the age group between 36-47months majority (57%) (62.5%) were found to have moderate malnutrition in the boys and girls group respectively. Age group of 48-59months majority (83.3%) (100%) boys and girls were found to have mild malnutrition respectively.

Table 2

Under-five Children's malnutrition classification according to gender (N=142)

Age	MALE							FEMALE						
	Mild		Moderate		Severe		Total	Mild		Moderate		Severe		Total
	f	%	F	%	f	%		f	%	F	%	f	%	
< 6 months	5	29.4	3	47	9	52.9	17	5	45.5	3	27.2	3	27.2	11
6 -11month	4	80	0	80	1	20	5	4	22.2	12	66.6	2	11	18
12-23months	0	0	9	75	3	25	12	14	51.8	8	29.6	4	14.8	27
24-35 months	0	0	6	42.8	8	57	14	6	75	2	25	0	0	8
36-47 months	2	14.2	8	57	4	28.5	14	3	37.5	5	62.5	0	0	8
48-59 months	5	83.3	0	0	1	16.6	6	2	100	0	0	0	0	2

Regression analyses of factors influencing for malnutrition

Malnutrition was a dependent variable and factors affecting the malnutrition score were independent variables. The regression analysis shown in the (table: 3) as factors influencing malnutrition increases malnutrition in under-five children also increases showed in (Fig:2). There is an apparent positive correlation between antenatal, weaning, and immunization status and illness factors and malnutrition ($p < 0.001$) indicating that for an increase of inadequate antenatal care (0.050), uncertain in providing exclusive breastfeeding up to 6month (0.146), inappropriate amount of nutritious food introduced during the weaning period and failure to continue breastfeeding up to 2years of age (0.024), failure to immunize as per national immunization schedule

and illness encountered during the under-five period (0.044) showed an increase in malnutrition and also showed malnutrition negatively correlated with diet /lifestyle during pregnancy ($p < 0.001$). It implies malnutrition is (-0.018) less with diet and lifestyle adopted during pregnancy.

Table 3

Regression analyses of factors influencing for malnutrition with malnutrition

Variables	Regression Coefficient(b)	SE(B)	t-value	Significance(p< 0.001)	95.% (CI)
Antenatal	0.050	0.078	0.638	0.524	-0.104 to 0.204
Diet and Lifestyle during Pregnancy	-0.018	0.083	-0.215	0.830	-0.183 to 0.147
Feeding pattern	0.146	0.084	1.739	0.084	-0.020 to 0.312
Weaning	0.024	0.056	0.435	0.664	-0.087 to 0.13
Immunization and Illness	0.044	0.071	0.630	0.530	-0.095 to 0.184
Constant	1.173				

Note: SE: Standard error; CI: Confidence interval.

Fig: 2 Scatter plot indicate the distribution of malnutrition against factor influencing malnutrition in under-five children

Association between malnutrition with demographic variables

Demographic variable (table4) computed $\chi^2 = 11.83$ of age in a month is less than the table value of $\chi^2 = 25.00$, for $\alpha = 0.05$ at df 15, there is acceptance of the research hypothesis. The χ^2 of gender (1.61), types of delivery (3.673), illness during pregnancy (5.750), mother's age at birth (4.178), parity (4.373), socio-economic status (4.449) is less than the table value of $\chi^2 = 7.81$, for $\alpha = 0.05$ at df 3, there is accept of research hypothesis. The χ^2 of the child who has undergone surgery (3.865), primary caretaker (6.942), age of the mother (4.178), age at marriage (6.463) is less than the table value of $\chi^2 = 12.59$, for $\alpha = 0.05$ at df 6, there is accept of research hypothesis. The χ^2 of birth order of the child (10.368), Number of siblings below 5 years (7.431) is less than the table value of $\chi^2 = 16.92$ for $\alpha = 0.05$ at df 9, the research hypothesis was accepted.

Table: 4 Association between malnutrition with demographic variables

SL. No	Demographic Variables	χ^2	df	Significance (p<0.05)
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1.	Age in month	11.83	15	0.691
	a. < 6 months			
	b. 6month-11month			
	c. 12–23 months			
	d. 24–35 months			
	e. 36–47 months			
	f. 48–59 months			
2.	Gender	1.61	3	0.73
	a. Male			
	b. Female			
3.	Types of delivery	3.673	3	0.299
	a. Normal			
	b. Caesarean			
4.	Illness during delivery	5.750	3	0.123
	a. Yes			
	b. No			
5.	Child has undergone any surgery	3.865	6	0.534
	a. Yes.			
	b. No			
6.	Birth order of the child	10.368	9	0.322
	a. First			
	b. Second			
	c. Third			
	d. More than four			
7.	No of sibling below 5years	7.431	9	0.592
	a. None			
	b. One			
	c. Two			
	d. More than three			
8.	Primary care taker	6.942	6	0.326
	a. Mother			
	b. Father			
	c. Grandparents			
	d. Others			
9.	Age of the mother	4.178	6	0.653
	a. Less than 18year			
	b. 18-22years			
	c. 23-25Years			
	d. 25years-30years			
	e. More than 30years			
10.	Age at marriage	6.463	6	0.373
	a. Less than 18years			
	b. 18-22years			
	c. 23-25Years			
	d. 25years-30years			
	e. More than 30years			
11.	Mother's age at child birth	4.178	3	0.653
	a. Less than 18years			
	b. 18-22years			
	c. 23-25Years			
	d. 25years-30years			
	e. More than 30years			

12.	Parity	4.373	3	0.224
	a. 1			
	b. 2			
	c. 3			
	d. More than four			
13.	Socio-Economic status	4.449	3	0.217
	a. APL			
	b. BPL			

Discussion

However, there have been many studies related to malnutrition assessment in India. The present study focused to identify how various factors influence malnutrition in under-five children in hospitalized under-five children. Most of the other studies preferred the WHO child growth standard chart to estimate the malnutrition percentile. In the present study, researchers identified mild-moderate and severe degrees of malnutrition by Gomez classification. Whereas most of the study felt Gomez classification is one of the oldest methods and it has more barriers to identify the malnutrition in under-five children but present study felt it was easy to identify the malnutrition in Gomez classification. A study conducted by Ghimire U, Aryal BK, Gupta AK, Sapkota S. Severe acute malnutrition and its associated factors among children under five years (2020) out of 398 under-five children, 5.8% were severely malnourished and the higher percentage of female children were malnourished[9]. The present study identified among 142 samples boys between the age group 24-35month were 57%severely malnutrition. The results of the community-based cross-sectional study revealed the prevalence of undernutrition was wasted 18.4%; underweight 38.3%; stunted 41.3%. Mothers who had four or more ANC visits and iron and folic acid intake(IFA) for 100 or more days had a lower prevalence of wasting, stunting, and underweight than the mothers with three or fewer ANC visits and inadequate IFA intake. Children with a history of prelacteal feeding had a high prevalence of stunting, underweight, and wasting.[18-19]The present study revealed majority (52.9%) of less than under five boys were severely malnutrition and (45.5%) of girls were of mild malnutrition. Age group of 6-11month majority (80%) boys were mild and moderate malnutrition and (66.6%) of the girls were moderately nourished. Between 12-23month the majority (75%) of boys were of moderate malnutrition and (29.6%) of the girls were moderately nourished. The majority (57%) of the boys between the age group of 24-35months showed severe malnutrition and (25%) girls were moderately nourished. Among the age group between 36-47months majority (57%) (62.5%) found moderate malnutrition in boys and girls groups respectively. Age group of 48-59months majority (83.3%) (100%) boys and girls were found to have mild malnutrition respectively.

Conclusion

Factors affecting malnutrition are relatively high among under-five children, assessment of malnutrition depends upon how the methodology is adopted; it is widely a challenge for the health care professionals for immediate identification. Strengthening public health intervention for mild malnutrition is important and effective implementation and evaluation is essential to prevent malnutrition among under-five in India.

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